

INTEGRATION OF EMOTIONAL INTELLIGENCE AND SPIRITUAL INTELLIGENCE IN TEACHER EDUCATION

Tajinder Kour (Research scholar)

&

Dr Jaspal Singh

Directorate of Distance Education

University of Jammu

Abstract

Emotional and Spiritual intelligence, no doubt in our times, got the popularity and in recent Days both are considered the integral part of intelligence. It is proved that a balanced personality, " A person who is emotionally as well as spiritually balanced can perform better in his academic, professional and general life." Now the need of the time is to create such balanced personalities in our class rooms and this crucial task to integrate the emotional and spiritual intelligence in teaching –learning process is in the hands of our teachers. This research paper highlights some basic problems of our present educational system and suggests a few relevant tips to integrate EQ and SQ in teacher education to overcome all these challenging problems. Because teachers are the real nation builders and there is no another way except taking the help of our teachers to create and build a humane society.

Introduction:

A growing number of educators are recognizing that the pursuit of an exclusively academic education leaves students ill-prepared for future challenges both as individuals and as members of society. Academic performance itself, as well as self-esteem, character, and human relationships, suffer when the education of the whole person is neglected. A new field of spiritual and emotional learning - has emerged from new understandings of the nature of intelligence, learning and success. In the 1980's, Howard Gardner introduced the concept of multiple intelligence, and soon educators began to see that they could respond to and cultivate not only cognitive intelligence, but a broad range of human capacities including interpersonal (social) and intrapersonal (emotional) intelligences (Frames of Mind, 1983) More recently, Daniel Goleman documented that emotional intelligence is a greater predictor of academic and life success than IQ. His concept of "emotional literacy" refers to the discovery that the emotional and spiritual skills of children can be cultivated as part of the school curriculum and that doing so enhances

cognitive learning and personal resiliency in the face of change and challenge. (Emotional Intelligence, 1995) In the same year. It highlights the truth that EQ and SQ are more important than IQ. The recent trends of research around the world, in our days, show the popularity of emotional intelligence as well as spiritual intelligence. But before taking into consideration our today topic, it is necessary to be familiar with two key words of this topic:

- 1) Emotional Intelligence
- 2) Spiritual Intelligence

According to Salovey and Mayer (1990), emotional intelligence is the capacity to both understand emotional information and reason with emotions. It is comprised of four primary abilities.

- 1) The capacity to accurately perceive emotions
- 2) The capacity to use emotions to facilitate thinking
- 3) The capacity to understand emotional meanings
- 4) The capacity to man manage emotions.

Goleman (1995) stated that 80% of a person’s success is relied on emotional intelligence compare to about 20% only of their IQ. The findings of this research are supported by Sternberg.

Sternberg Found out that IQ’s influence towards a person’s success is limited to 4% of variance It is so obvious that a human being have various emotions and feelings such as happy, shy, sad, boring, scared and others, but the way to control and balance these different type of emotions differs from person to person. Emotional Intelligence (EI) is a group of mental abilities which could help the individual to identify and understand the feelings of one’s own and others. It could increase the ability to control our feelings.

Skills of emotional intelligence

Daniel Goleman divided Emotional Intelligence into ‘Personal’ and ‘Social’ competences, which broadly split between personal and interpersonal skills on Skills You Need. Within each of these sections are a range of skills which are the elements of emotional intelligence.

Personal Skills or Competences	Social Skills or Competences
How we manage ourselves	How we handle relationships with others
<input type="checkbox"/> Self-awareness <ul style="list-style-type: none"> <input type="radio"/> Emotional awareness <input type="radio"/> Accurate self-assessment <input type="radio"/> Self-confidence 	<input type="checkbox"/> Empathy <ul style="list-style-type: none"> <input type="radio"/> Understanding others <input type="radio"/> Developing others <input type="radio"/> Service orientation

<input type="checkbox"/> Self-regulation <ul style="list-style-type: none"> ○ Self-control ○ Trustworthiness ○ Conscientiousness ○ Adaptability ○ Innovation <input type="checkbox"/> Motivation <ul style="list-style-type: none"> ○ Achievement drive ○ Commitment ○ Initiative ○ Optimism 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ○ Leveraging diversity ○ Political awareness <input type="checkbox"/> Social Skills <ul style="list-style-type: none"> ○ Influence ○ Communication ○ Conflict management ○ Leadership ○ Change catalyst ○ Building bonds ○ Collaboration and cooperation ○ Team capabilities
---	---

2) **Spiritual intelligence:** In general, however, spirituality is viewed as beliefs, practices, and experiences that shape and create a way of knowing and living that may or may not be informed by religious ritual, tradition, and doctrine. A person often inherits religion, but makes the conscious choice to practice spirituality by seeking answers about the self, universe, and meaning of life. While numerous [scientists](#) propose that spirituality is a developmental process, they disagree on how the process occurs. Some suggest we are born with spiritual capacity that is cultivated (or not) through interaction with parents, teachers, and our culture. Others think spiritual development occurs in stages as we integrate our beliefs with our feelings and actions.

Spiritual intelligence can be defined as the ability to create meaning based on deep understanding of existential questions, and awareness of the ability to use multiple levels of consciousness in problem solving (Vaughan, 2002).

MacDonald (2002) review many definitions of spirituality and identify several common themes .Based on these themes, spirituality can be defined as:

- (a) Focus on ultimate meaning
- (b) Awareness and development of multiple levels of consciousness
- (c) Experience of the preciousness and sacredness of life
- (d) Transcendence of self into a greater whole.

Emmons attempts to integrate spirituality into the framework of intelligence, and argues that spirituality can be viewed as a form of intelligence because it predicts functioning and adaptation (e.g. better health)

and offers capabilities that enable people to solve problems and attain goals. He proposes four components for Spiritual Intelligence:

- (a) Ability to utilize spiritual resources to solve problems
- (b) Ability to enter into heightened states of consciousness
- (c) Ability to invest everyday activities and relationships with a sense of the sacred and
- (d) Capacity for transcendence more experiential elements of spirituality

Spiritual Intelligence (SQ) Skills

<p>Higher Self/Ego self Awareness</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Awareness of own worldview • Awareness of life purpose (mission) • Awareness of values hierarchy • Complexity of inner thought • Awareness of Ego self/ Higher Self 	<p>Universal Awareness</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Awareness of interconnectedness of all life • Awareness of worldviews of others • Breadth of time perception • Awareness of limitations/power of human perception • Awareness of Spiritual laws • Experience of transcendent oneness
<p>Higher Self/Ego self Mastery</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Commitment to spiritual growth • Keeping Higher Self in charge • Living your purpose and values • Sustaining your faith • Seeking guidance from Higher Power or Higher Self 	<p>Social Mastery / Spiritual Presence</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • A wise and effective spiritual teacher/mentor • A wise and effective change agent • Makes compassionate and wise decisions • A calming, healing presence • Being aligned with the ebb and flow of life

Need Of Integrating Emotional And Spiritual Intelligence In Teacher Education:

Now what is the need to integrate emotional and spiritual intelligence into the field of teaching –learning especially in areas of teacher education keeping in mind different problems of present school system? How it will be effective for building or building a humane society? Today, our education is treated more as a skill grafting mechanism. Rather than a process of transforming human being. We treated our schools, colleges and universities as factories, where an input of lesser value is placed –in and which ultimately release an output of higher value. We are producing the learners of high intelligence rather than the learners equipped with the life skills that are used by an individual at every moment of life in various situations –conflicting or general and therefore are considered as the building blocks of one’s behaviour. These need to be learnt well and adequately to lead a healthy, meaningful and productive li rather than a

process of transforming human being. We treated our schools, colleges and universities as factories, where an input of lesser value is placed–in and which ultimately release an output of higher value. We are producing the learners of high intelligence rather than the learners equipped with the life skills that are used by an individual at every moment of life in various situations –conflicting or general and therefore are considered as the building blocks of one’s Behaviour. These need to be learnt well and adequately to lead a healthy, meaningful and productive life. As being teachers we neglected the real purpose of our education which is meant to transform the individuals and society to higher levels of physicals, intellectual, social, emotional, aesthetic, moral and spiritual attainments. It enabled and equipped the learners for the job market but not for life. Recently our school system is facing so many challenging problems like theft, bullying, ragging, rapes, and even for murder. This is because of ill treatment of our students in their classrooms, mal administration of educational institutions, and etc. Diminishing social norms is also an important matter here. India is also witnessing the incidents of juvenile delinquency. Reports show that the problem of student stress and aggression is increasing day by day. This is a drastic challenge before us. Now, the question is why we want to integrate EQ and SQ in the process of teacher education? In response to this question I would like to quote here the words of J. Krishnamurti,”

The highest function of education is to bring about an integrated individual who is capable of dealing with life as a whole.” So our education must foster self-esteem, leadership, tolerance, ethical judgment and moral reasoning. It must also stimulate learners to consider a variety of perspectives on some of the fundamental questions posed by the human condition: “what is truth”, “what is reality”, and “what are my duties to my fellow men, to my country and to GOD. The next and the main thing is that how can we create the integrated personalities in our class rooms. The task is not easy and simple because we are dealing with living material that is made up of brain full of unique mental abilities, emotions, feelings, spiritual essence etc. Here the role of teachers as the creators is so important because they are responsible for this crucial task. They are the real molders of this living material. They have to create such type of class room environment where the equal recognition will be given to the different domains of the learners i.e. cognitive, affective and conative. They must ensure that they are working upon mind as well as heart, spirit and body. The following are some suggestions for the teachers to create such type of environment the EQ and SQ can be nourished with IQ of the learners. But the teacher’s level of EQ and SQ is by far the single where most important variable for this task. A teacher must handle his or her own emotions, especially the negative one, in an authentic, real and healthy way. Here is an outline for the teachers:1

Managing Their (Teachers) Own Emotions: –Teachers have to –

- a) Identify their own feelings
- b) Take responsibility for them
- b) Use their emotional awareness to learn about their self
- c) Work on keeping their area of acceptance wide open

2 Helping Their Students Feel Better Through Increased EQ

- a) Help them label their feelings
- b) Give them real choices
- c) Respect their feelings
- d) Validation accept their feelings by showing understanding, empathy caring and concerne) Empower them-to solve their own problems using empathy, compassion and m mutual respect for each other’s feelings
- f) Avoid labels and judgment –avoid “shoulds”-avoid good/bad; nice/rude etc.Now here are some specific traits of a positive variable for this task. A teacher must handle his or her own emotions, especially the negative one, in anauthentic, real and healthy way. Here is an outline for the teachers:1

Managing Their (Teachers) Own Emotions:-Teachers have to –

- a) Identify their own feelings
- b) Take responsibility for them
- c)Use their emotional awareness to learn about their self
- d) Work on keeping their area of acceptance wide open

2 Helping Their Students Feel Better Through Increased EQ

- a) Help them label their feelings
- b) Give them real choices
- c) Respect their feelings
- d) Validation –accepts their feelings by showing understanding, empathy, caring and concern) Empower them –to solve their own problems using empathy, compassion and mutual respect for each other’s feelings
- f) Avoid labels and judgment –avoid “should”-avoid good/bad; nice/rude etc.Now here are some specific traits of a positive learning environment which can be kept in mind during the process of teaching-learning:

Safe Environment which is free from threats, force, punishment, coercion, manipulation, pressure, stress, intimidation, humiliation, embarrassment, invalidation.

- 2) Respectful environment for each other's feelings, emotional needs beliefs, values and uniqueness.
- 3) Emotionally Intelligent environment where feelings are valued, discussed, validated. EI is part of the formal and informal curriculum.
- 4) The Relevant/Meaningful/Practical study material which can help students with real problems in their lives. Life skills, relationship skills and parenting skills are taught.
- 5) Empathetic & Caring environment for both teachers and students.
- 6) Interesting/Stimulating environment for students to learn more and more in their life.
- 7) Flexible environment for all those Changes that are made frequently, easily and smoothly
- 8) Individual/Supportive/Nurturing environment where students are treated individually. Their individual needs, talents, potential and interests are supported.

In concluding words

The concept of *Emotional Intelligence*, which integrates *emotions* into *rationality*, emerges in this stage. It is the unique intersection of *Heart* and *head*, working together. If valued at work, emotional intelligence promises distinguishing success through empathy, compassion and motivation. *Spiritual Intelligence* comes into scene with all its promising transformative and binding power. It integrates reason and emotion – the mind and the heart, providing the self with meaning-giving centre. Through spiritual intelligence, one learns how to be comfortable with questions, even if they do not have formulized answers, and thus to cope with ambiguity of life and work. “The individuals who have a good combination of spiritual and emotional intelligence that is harmonized with their intellectuals could produce a balanced generation.

References

- Goleman, D. (1998). Working With Emotional Intelligence. New York, NY. Bantum Books.
- Vaugahan, F. What is Spiritual Intelligence? Journal of Humanistic Psychology Vol. 42, No.2 Spring 2002 Sage Publication.
- Mayer, J. (2000). Spiritual intelligence—or spiritual consciousness? The International Journal for the Psychology of Religion, 10, 47–56.
- Panday, Manju & Maikhuri, Rama .(2005) Teaching Attitude of Effective and In effective Teachers. Psycho Lingua, 35, pp.87-90.

Salovey, Peter; Mayer, John; Caruso, David (2004), "Emotional Intelligence: Theory, Findings, and Implications", *Psychological Inquiry*, pp. 197–215

Zohar and Marshall. (2000). *SQ: Spiritual intelligence: The ultimate intelligence*. London: Bloomsbury.
www.academia.edu